

A Research on Sustainable Environmental Awareness of University Students: The Case of Selçuk University

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ABSTRACT

The resources on earth are not sufficient to meet the demands of people. Insufficient resources include many problems such as effective and efficient use, fair sharing, transmission to future generations. Individuals, states, non-governmental organizations, international organizations, international companies are engaged in important activities regarding the use of economic resources. They carry out activities aimed at raising awareness on issues such as adequate production, consumption sufficient for the needs, efficient and effective resource use, increasing recycling, less pollution. Environmental awareness is a very important issue that should be given and reinforced in the family, at school, in the environment, in working life. Because the protection of the environment and taking the necessary measures in this regard is an issue that concerns not only people living today, but also future generations. Therefore, the inclusion of courses containing environmental awareness in educational institutions, the acquisition of topics in activities such as panels, seminars and symposiums will increase the sensitivity to the environment. In this study, the topic of sustainable environment is explained. A survey application was conducted to measure the awareness and sensitivity of Selçuk University students about the sustainable environment.

Keywords: Environment, Sustainable Environment, Environmental Awareness.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the beginning of its history, man saw himself as a part of nature. Hunting and gathering, which he does to satisfy the need for nutrition, are actually the first economic behaviors. New inventions that have made life easier over time have increased human beings' desire or appetite to dominate or control nature a little more.

As a matter of fact, with the discovery of fire, man caused the destruction of forests and thus initiated the first environmental destruction (Backhouse, 1991:112). Events such as the industrial revolution, the use of steam power, the transition to mass production, the incredible development of technology and science have increased human intervention in the environment. However, wherever the human being's hand touches, environmental destruction is taking place.

The discourse that economic resources are limited and human needs are unlimited has prepared the ground for the crude use of natural resources. Excessive consumption, production based on excessive profit ambitions, activities that cause negative externalities, the delivery of all kinds of goods and services to all parts of the world by multinational companies have led to the use of natural resources more than necessary or needed. Even the policies, advertising and marketing strategies that wildly increase consumption in order to overcome the recession in the economy have caused the idea that there is no harm from excessive consumption to settle in the memory of society.

As a result of the production and consumption frenzy experienced, the point reached in the world today is unjust income and wealth distribution, wars, economic crises, poverty, moral corruption, deep intercommunal camps and finally environmental massacres.

Giving priority to economic development (Uslu, 1996:3) has actually deepened the problems. In this study, it was tried to measure the environmental awareness and sensitivity of university students, attitudes and behaviors towards the environment, consumption behaviors and habits in the context of environmental sustainability.

1.1. The Concept of the Environment and Environmental Problems

The branches of science that exist in every field are necessarily related to the human subject. What is happening in the environment in which we live will affect a person directly or indirectly, today or tomorrow. The environment is defined as the mixture of all living and inanimate beings surrounding the organism, the sum of external conditions and situations affecting the individual (Uluğ, 1997:41). The environment is the physical, biological, social, economic and cultural environment in which all living things maintain their relationships and interactions with each other throughout their lives (Öğrenveren, 2012:25). Together with man and all other living beings, it is the whole of nature and the human product objects in nature (Kırlioğlu and Can, 1998:3). The environment is the environment in which the activities of an organization are carried out, covering the relationships between natural resources such as air, water, soil (Çukacı, 2003:92). The environment refers to everything that affects itself and the organism (New Age, 2024).

In the last century, the consumption of natural resources by humans faster than the rate of self-renewal has caused environmental problems. These problems have become a threat to the future of both humans, other living beings and even inanimate beings. Households, governments, private sector enterprises, non-governmental organizations, etc. in the formation of environmental problems there are many actors who have influence (Akıncı and Akıncı, 2010:193).

Environmental mobilization has also increased in the world along with environmental problems. Since environmental problems know no borders, it has become necessary for each country to take responsibility for the future of the world (Eyyübi, 2004:i). The size of environmental problems has increased to a magnitude that can no longer be limited only by environmental pollution. However, the biggest factor in the environmental problems reaching these dimensions can be expressed as the increase in environmental pollution (Küçüker, 2017:6). However, at the current point, the types and dimensions of environmental problems have increased significantly.

Environmental problems are usually caused by individuals. Individuals as consumers and producers do not take into account the environment when performing their activities. These activities increase the pressure on the environment and exceed the capacity that the environment can bear. Although the types of pressure on the environment vary according to the level of development of societies; today, environmental problems are no longer local or regional, but are now evaluated on a global scale. Environmental issues were initially taken into consideration at the national level. However, after the 1970s, it started to be discussed at the international level and the environment has become an element of sustainable development. In this context, the most important studies related to environmental sensitivity in the world are as follows: Stockholm Environmental Conference (1972), Mediterranean Action Plan (1974), Brundtland Report (1983), Rio Conference (1992), Kyoto Protocol (1997), UN Millennium Summit (2000), World Development Summit (2002) (Aksu, 2011:11-19).

1.2. Environmental Awareness and Environmental Education

It is possible to understand the nature of increasing environmental problems, to develop solutions and to bring about changes in individuals' attitudes and behaviors related to the environment thanks to environmental education. It is a well-known fact that individuals who have received a good education about the environment and have gained environmental sensitivity play a more active role in solving environmental problems. In order for people to have a safer and healthier environment, it is necessary to gain the necessary knowledge and skills by receiving environmental-related trainings (Özbuğutu et al., 2014:394).

Individuals who feel responsible towards their environment choose the least negative way and method to the environment while producing and consuming in their daily lives (Ünlü, 1992:8). In the field studies conducted, it has been found that the sensitivity to the environment increases as the level of education and culture increases (Yaraş, 2011). Consumers with high environmental awareness usually have high income and education levels as well. They have a lot of daily reading time, they do research on the Internet to get information about products when shopping, and they watch environmental programs and news frequently.

Environmental education, which provides the education of environmentally conscious individuals, is an indispensable tool for the elimination of problems that deeply affect the whole world. Environmental education both conveys ecological information and ensures the development of attitudes towards the environment in individuals and the transformation of these attitudes into behavior. People who receive environmental education develop cognitive, affective and psycho-motor learning areas (Erten, 2004:3).

Companies and trademarks aim to bring their customers who demand their goods and services under a constant influence from rational, emotional and ethical points of view in order not to lose them to rival companies (Tıgılı et al., 2007: 84). However, it is observed that conscious consumers also take into account the companies that produce the goods and services they consume. Brand-related associations include both consumers' attitudes about the product and their perceptions about the company's environmental policies (Singh et al., 2008: 599).

Environmental pollution should not be considered only as damage to nature and depletion of resources. Finally, the fact that environmental pollution is the end of civilization and historical-cultural assets should not be forgotten (Merchant, 1992:25). After contamination or deterioration occurs, the costs of correcting them will be much higher than the costs of taking precautions from the beginning (Uçman, 2018). That is why the increase in constructive behavior towards the environment is based on education and awareness. It is not enough that only environmental-related courses are included in the curriculum. In order for environmental education to be more permanent in practice, activities should be organized that will allow students to get out of the physical classroom environment and get to know nature closely.

1.3. Sustainable Environment

In the Brundtland Commission of the United Nations in 1987, sustainability is defined as meeting the needs of today without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (UN, 2025a). Activities are carried out by many voluntary or compulsory organizations for the protection of nature and the environment and the transmission of this to future generations. Sustainability and sustainable environment issues have come to the fore in order for these activities to become continuous. Sustainability is the ability of objects and processes in general to maintain and maintain the ability to change and therefore develop

(Çağlar, 1998:69). In fact, the concept of sustainability was born due to the concern about the deterioration of economic and social development following the deterioration of natural resources.

Sustainability includes many factors such as economic, social, historical, human and cultural. The economic dimension of sustainability, which is usually popular, is being examined a lot. But the social dimension is also important. As a matter of fact, social problems such as the unfair distribution of income and resources, the division of society into economic classes that will harm social peace, constitute the social dimension of sustainability, which also focuses on future generations. For a strong socio-economic model to be constructed, conditions such as the minimum use of non-renewable resources, meeting basic needs for living humanely, giving importance to personal rights and freedoms, and protecting the natural environment must be established (Ceylan, 2010:15).

Regarding the sustainability of the environment in Türkiye, the 1982 Constitution says that citizens and the private sector, especially public institutions, have duties. "Everyone has the right to live in a healthy and balanced environment. It is the duty of the state and citizens to improve the environment, protect environmental health and prevent environmental pollution. The state organizes the planning and provision of services to health institutions from a single source in order to ensure that everyone continues their life in physical and mental health; to realize cooperation by increasing savings and efficiency in human and material power. The state fulfills this duty by taking advantage of health and social institutions in the public and private sectors and supervising them" (Constitution of 1982, m.56).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous studies have been conducted for university students on environmental sensitivity, attitudes and behaviors towards the environment, sustainable environmental awareness.

In the doctoral study titled "University Youth's Attitudes towards the Environment and Environmental Problems" conducted by Şama (1997), the attitudes and behaviors of the students of the faculty of education towards the environment were examined. In the research called "Attitudes of Second Grade Students towards Environment and Environmental Problems" conducted by Erol (2005), it was aimed to determine the interests and behaviors of university students towards environment and environmental problems and their environmental awareness. In the research titled "Investigation of the Effect of Student-Centered Teaching on the Environmental Literacy Level of Teacher Candidates" by Kışoğlu (2009), the contribution of 60 biology teacher candidates who started university education to determining environmental awareness and student-centered practice in environmental health course to teacher candidates' environmental literacy was investigated. Şerenli (2010) In his study titled "Determining the Levels of Environmental Educators of the Future to Have Environmental Literacy Components (The Case of Muğla University)"; It was aimed to determine the possible relationships between the environmental literacy levels of prospective teachers and their demographic characteristics. Oğuz et al. (2011) in their study titled "Environmental Awareness of Students in Higher Education", they carried out a survey application aimed at environmental awareness of students studying in higher education. Timur et al. (2012) In the study "Investigation of Environmental Behaviors of Science and Technology Teachers and Teacher Candidates" conducted by, the behavior of science and technology teachers and science and technology teacher candidates towards the environment with various variables was compared. In this study, it was concluded that teachers' attitudes and behaviors towards the environment were observed by students and caused them to become role models. The

research conducted by Hoang and Kato (2016) reveals that the environmental awareness of students is limited and the education provided is insufficient.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. The Purpose, Importance and Scope of the Research

With this study, it was aimed to measure the environmental awareness of Selcuk University students. In line with the conducted study, a literature review was conducted first and the theoretical framework of the research was established. 6 hypotheses have been formed about the research. The hypotheses developed in accordance with the subject and application scope of the study are as follows:

H1- Gender reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness.

H2- Age reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness.

H3- Marital status reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness.

H4- The year of residence reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness.

H5- The section reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness.

H6- Monthly income status reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness.

3.2. The Universe of the Research and the Sample

The universe of the study consists of university students studying in the spring semester of 2024-2025. Associate and undergraduate students who are studying at Selcuk University in the spring semester of 2023-2024 constitute the sample of this study.

As of 2025 there are more than 70.000 students at Selcuk University. Out of a total of 550 surveys conducted with Selcuk University students, 516 of them were included in the analysis because they were scientifically usable. 34 the survey was not included in the analysis because it was not scientifically usable.

3.3. Data Collection Tool and Scales

In order to test the hypotheses established within the scope of the research, the survey technique was used to obtain the research data. In the preparation of the questionnaire form, the survey data from Çelikbaş (2016)'s study "The Impact of Sustainability-Based Environmental Education on Secondary School Students' Environmental Behaviors and Sustainable Environmental Attitudes" were applied to Selçuk University students.

A questionnaire form consisting of two parts has been developed to complete the application part of the study. In the first part of the survey, questions about demographic information are asked, while in the second part there are 25 variables related to sustainable environmental awareness. Students were asked to answer these variables according to the 5-point Likert scale (1: Strongly Agree, 2: Agree, 3: Neither Agree nor Disagree, 4: Disagree, 5: Strongly Disagree).

4. THE FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

Of the 516 participants whose questionnaire was evaluated, 240 (46.5%) were men and 276 (53.5%) were women. 230 students (44.6%) are in the age range of 18-20, 247 (47.9%) are in the age range of 21-25, 23 (4.5%) are in the age range of 26-30, 16 (3.1%) are in the age range of 30 and over. 34 (6.6%) of the students are married and 480 (93.0%) of them are single. Students from 25 different departments participated in the survey application. 213 (41,3) of the students have monthly income less than TL 10.000, 150 (29,1) 10.001-20.000 TL, 33 (6,4%) 20.001-30.000 TL, 49 (9,5%) 30.001-40.000 TL and 70 (13,6%) have monthly income status of TL 40.001 and above.

The analyses were performed by Mann-Whitney-U and Kruskal-Wallis tests, as the ‘P’ value was less than 0.05 and distributed homogeneously in accordance with the normality test.

Table 1: Reliability in Likert Type Scales (Research Application)

Scales	Cronbach’s Alpha	Number of Expressions
Sustainable Environmental Awareness	0,896	25

According to these results (Table 1), the reliability of the students in terms of sustainable environmental awareness from the scales of the survey is good compared to $9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$.

Table 2: Mann-Whitney U Test for Sustainable Environmental Awareness by Gender

Gender	Number of People (N)	Average	Mann-Whitney	P
Man	240	265,47	3,144	0,322
Women	276	252,44		

According to Table 2, as a result of the Mann-Whitney-U test, there is no significant difference between the gender's scores for sustainable environmental awareness ($P > 0.05$). Dec. Accordingly, the averages and average scores of men and women are close to each other or the same. According to these results, gender does not reveal significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness, and the hypothesis established as (H1) is not supported.

Table 3: Kruskal-Wallis Test for Sustainable Environmental Awareness by Age

Age	Number of People (N)	Average	Kruskal – Wallis	P
18-20	230	294,78	34,216	0,000
21-25	247	229,37		
26-30	23	290,76		
30 +	16	140,22		

According to Table 3, as a result of the Kruskal-Wallis test, there is a significant difference between the age Decency environmental awareness scores ($P < 0.05$). The average scores of the students vary according to age. according to the Kruskal-Wallis test ($P = 0.000 < 0.05$), a significant difference was found that people between the ages of 18 and 20 had a higher average score than people over the age of 30. According to these results, age reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness, and the hypothesis established as (H2) is supported.

Table 4: Mann-Whitney-U Test for Sustainable Environmental Awareness According to Marital Status

Marital Status	Number of People (N)	Average	Mann-Whitney	P
Married	34	186,12	3,300	0,004
Single	480	262,56		

According to Table 4, as a result of the Mann-Whitney-U test, it reveals a significant difference between the scores of marital status towards sustainable environmental awareness ($P < 0.05$). The average scores of the students vary according to their marital status. According to the Mann-Whitney-U test ($P = 0.004 < 0.05$), a significant difference was found that single students had more scores than married students. According to these results, marital status reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness and the hypothesis established as (H4) is supported.

Table 5: Kruskal-Wallis Testi for Sustainable Environmental Awareness by Year of Residence

Year of Residence	Number of People (N)	Average	Kruskal – Wallis	P
less than 1 year	76	255,80	36,588	0,000
1-2 years	97	226,55		
2-4 years	88	216,53		
more than 4 years	251	343,30		

According to Table 5, as a result of the Kruskal-Wallis test, there was a significant difference between sustainable environmental awareness scores according to the year of residence ($P < 0.05$). The average scores of the students vary according to the year of residence. Students who have been living in Konya for more than 4 years have a higher average score between 2-4 years than students living in Konya, and this score reveals a significant difference according to the Kruskal-Wallis test ($P = 0.000 < 0.05$). According to these results, the year of residence reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness, and the hypothesis established as (H4) is supported.

Kruskal-Wallis Test for Sustainable Environmental Awareness by Department: The survey was applied in 25 different departments such as accounting, communication, law, business administration, tourism, medicine, philosophy, sports. As a result of the Kruskal-Wallis test, there is a significant difference between the department's scores for sustainable environmental awareness ($0.00 < 0.05$). According to the department, the average scores of students towards sustainable environmental awareness vary. According to these results, the department reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness and the (H5) hypothesis is supported.

Table 6: Kruskal-Wallis Test for Sustainable Environmental Awareness by Income Status

Income(TL)	Number of People (N)	Average	Kruskal-Wallis	P
Under 10.000	213	265,34	13,573	0,009
10.001-20.000TL	150	273,29		
20.001-30.000	33	288,36		
30.001-40.000	49	199,89		
40.001and above	70	229,25		

According to Table 6, as a result of the Kruskal-Wallis test, it reveals a significant difference between the scores of income status towards sustainable environmental awareness ($0.009 < 0.05$). The average scores of the students vary according to the sustainable environmental awareness. According to these results, the monthly income situation reveals significant differences in terms of university students' environmental awareness and the (H6) hypothesis is supported.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In the study, an academic study was conducted in accordance with the previously determined goals and some results were reached as a result of the analyses. With the analysis conducted in the light of the data revealed by the survey application, 6 hypotheses were tested and 5 of them were accepted. As a result of the Mann-Whitney-U and Kruskal-Wallis tests, it was found that while age, marital status, income status, department and year of residence revealed significant differences in students' sustainable environmental awareness, gender did not reveal significant differences.

In Türkiye, important steps are being taken to ensure that society has access to environmental information. Public participation is ensured in rural development and environmental impact assessment processes. As a matter of fact, protests against the suspension and cancellation of projects that will negatively affect the environment are frequently encountered. In addition, numerous civil initiatives related to environmental problems have been established in recent years (İstemil, 2008:40). Environmental problems are local problems, so the priority in determining and solving them is for local governments (Güzel, 2018). As a matter of fact, the task of collecting, accumulating, transporting and making harmless the production and consumption wastes generated due to economic activities in Türkiye under appropriate conditions has been left to local governments (Çondur and Cömertler, 2010:68). Therefore, it would be appropriate to give local governments authority over local financial instruments and to use the funds generated in the areas of environmental protection, sustainability and raising awareness of local people.

An education system should be established that gives students environmental awareness (Yücel, 2003:115). Educational institutions and local government organizations should cooperate on the dissemination and internalization of environmental awareness. In order to achieve the greatest environmental, economic and social impact, the best sustainability practices should be shared and worked together by their practitioners (EPA, 2024). Compensating, punishing, banning or imposing additional taxes on companies that cause negative externality for the damage they have caused to the environment are powers and autonomy that strengthen local governments. Providing incentives or tax breaks to companies

that cause positive externality will also help to protect the environment and transfer it to future generations (Bilgin and Orkunoglu, 2010, 80). Although environmental awareness is present in individuals, the relationship between this awareness and behavioral decisions is complex and not simple (Zhang et al., 2024:2). Many studies reveal that the environmental awareness of students is limited and the education provided is insufficient (Hoang and Kato, 2016:274, 285; Ishak et al., 2016:268; Quispe et al., 2025:19; Derman & Senemoğlu, 2015:78-79). Many substances and materials such as household wastes, chemical wastes, batteries and accumulators, organic wastes, concrete and iron wastes, car tires, electronic wastes, textiles, wood and metal products can be recycled (Sürmeli, 2011:37). When determining strategies to end poverty and other deprivations, improve health and education, reduce income inequality and promote economic development, combating climate change and protecting the oceans and forests should be taken into account (UN, 2025b). It is important that the technologies aimed at ensuring the protection and sustainability of the environment and the investments containing these technologies are put into practice. Environmental sensitivity also stands out in the investment decisions of enterprises that aim at sustainable development (Keijers, 2002:352).

Bees enable the pollination of some fruits. Predators such as snakes, birds and foxes keep some rodent populations under control (UNDP, 2024). Then man does not mean everything on this planet. When determining strategies to end poverty and other deprivations, improve health and education, reduce income inequality and promote economic development, combating climate change and protecting the oceans and forests should be taken into account (UN, 2025b).

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